

1 **The E7 protein of HPV42.**

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7 We conclude from study of whole transcription in cells with ectopic expression of the E7 viral protein from
8 HPV type 16 or type 42 some level of equivalence in transformation or oncogenic potential in HPV42 E7
9 as in the classical high-risk type HPV16. Keratin changes were similar following expression of E7 from
10 either type (*Krt6a* and *Krt6b*), with induction of *Brca1* and *Brca2* by both HPV42 and HPV16 E7.
11 Homeobox modulation was unique by HPV42 E7 involving Hmgb3. *Abca1* was silenced following
12 expression of E7 of either type. *Klk7* and *Klk10* kallikrein control was a conserved property of HPV41 and
13 HPV16 E7. Cells activated cycling in response to expression of either HPV16 E7 or HPV42 E7, marked by
14 *Pcna*.

15 Citations

16 1. Burmann, S.N., Wieland, U., Silling, S., Oellig, F., Chromy, D., Hyun, J., Gambichler, T. and
17 Kreuter, A., 2025. HPV42—a human papillomavirus classified as a low-risk type with oncogenic potential.
18 JDDG: Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft.

19 GSE196217